

Excess Molar Volumes of some Polyether + Water Systems

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Excess molar volumes at 25°, are reported for the system 1,2-dimethoxyethane + water and 12-crown-4 + water across their entire respective composition ranges. These data have been compared to others taken from the literature, in an effort to assess the effects of replacing hydroxy by methoxy groups, of switching linear to cyclic polyethers and of inserting oxyethylene groups

The data sets were analysed using a segmented composition model in order to obtain a quantitative description of the composition dependence of the excess molar volumes. Excess partial molar volumes of the organic species at infinite aqueous dilution were evaluated by means of four segment analyses of the various excess volume data sets. The effectiveness of the group additivity principle is nicely demonstrated.

Most of the recent research that has been carried out in our respective laboratories over the past few years has been concerned with the measurement, analysis and interpretation of the excess thermodynamic properties of the aqueous mixtures of alkyl polyethylene glycol monoethers¹⁻³. The composition dependence of thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures has proved to be a useful indicator of the existence of significant effects resulting from intermolecular interactions. It has been observed that the plots of the Gibbs function are not very informative. On the contrary, the composition dependence of the excess molar volumes (V^E), the first derivatives of G , may exhibit interesting composition dependence originating from variations in the modes of molecular aggregation. Indeed, such quantities are dominated primarily by chemical and intramolecular effects.

Our foregoing works have been mainly focused upon derivatives of polyethylene glycols, particularly ethylene glycol itself⁴. We addressed different types of structural modification¹⁻⁴: (i) variation of alkyl chain length for species with the same polar head group, (ii) variation of the polar head group(s) for species with the same alkyl tail, and (iii) branching

in the alkyl group for isomeric species.

The present work is mainly devoted to the study of the changes arising from the polar head group(s). With that in mind, we thought it worthwhile to report some values that we have measured for the excess molar volumes of [dimethyl ethylene glycol (CH₃OC₂H₄OCH₃) + water] and of [12-crown-4 {(C₂H₄O)₄} + water]. Our primary interest in the former system was to compare the excess molar volumes of the three systems [dimethyl ethylene glycol + water] (those reported here, together with literature data⁵), [2-methoxyethanol (CH₃OC₂H₄OH) + water]^{2,6} and [1,2-ethanediol (HOC₂H₄OH) + water]^{4,7}. We were also interested in comparing the excess molar volumes of [dimethyl ethylene glycol + water] with those obtained for [dimethyl diethylene glycol {CH₃O(C₂H₄O)₂H} + water]^{8,9} and [dimethyl triethylene glycol {CH₃O(C₂H₄O)₃H} + water]^{8,10}. We found also interesting to compare the excess molar volumes of the cyclic analog of dimethyl ethylene glycol, i.e. [1,4-dioxane{(C₂H₄O)₂} + water]^{11,12}, and those of [12-crown-4 + water] with values obtained for its linear analog [CH₃(OC₂H₄)₃OCH₃ + water]^{8,10}. We remark that 1,4-dioxane might be considered as the lower homolog,

6-crown-2, of the family of crown-ethers, 3n-crown-n, although it is not a crown-ether in the accepted sense of that term. We note that the free energies and entropies of transfer of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions from water to some of these hydroorganic solvents have been determined and discussed in terms of the ability of the organic component to induce enhancement or disruption of the three-dimensional tetrahedral structures of water in the water-rich region^{13,14}.

Results and Discussion

The results of our investigations will be presented in two parts. In the first one, we shall be concerned with visual appraisal of plots of excess molar volumes against mole fractional composition. Our intention is to explore the sensitivity of the composition dependence of the excess molar volumes to variations in the molecular structures of the amphiphiles. The second part will deal with the optimised four-segment model parameters that we have obtained for the data sets at our disposal.

The densities that were obtained for the pure substances are given in Table 1, together with some values taken from the literature^{5,15,17}.

TABLE 1—DENSITY OF THE PURE SOLVENTS AT 25°

Solvent	ρ^* (kg m ⁻³)	
	This work	Lit.
Water	—	997.048 ^a
Dimethoxyethane	862.62	860.5 ^b 863.7 ^c
12-Crown-4	1107.80	— ^d

^aRef. 15. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 16. ^dRef. 17.

The excess molar volume values for the two systems we measured are shown in Tables 2 and 3. Our density values for (1,2-dimethoxyethane + water) are consistent with those reported⁵, but appear to have a better level of internal consistency. Literature reveals that the composition dependence of isentropic compressibilities of several (a crown-ether + water) systems, has been studied. That implies that density measurements have been performed; unfortunately, no data are available¹⁷. The excess molar volumes of (1,2-dimethoxyethane + water) are shown in

Fig. 1, together with those for (2-methoxyethanol + water)^{2,6} and (1,2-ethanediol + water)^{4,7}. There is a very obvious increase in the magnitudes of the excess molar volumes with each substitution of a methyl group for an hydroxyl hydrogen. This might be related to the enhanced hydrophilic characteristics of the organic component of the binary mixtures. Not so clear-out appear the variations of V^E with each addition of a $-\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4-$ group in the molecule of 1,2-dimethoxyethane. Fig. 2 shows the composition dependence of excess molar volumes in respective systems [1,2-dimethoxyethane ($\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3$) + water], [dimethyl diethylene glycol $\{\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{OCH}_3\}$ + water] and [dimethyl triethylene glycol $\{\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{OCH}_3\}$ + water].

TABLE 2—EXCESS MOLAR VOLUMES FOR (1,2-DIMETHOXYETHANE + WATER) MIXTURES AT 25°

x	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	x	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0	0	0.182 8	-1.490 9
0.019 9	-0.198 8	0.186 9	-1.499 4
0.025 4	-0.260 1	0.199 5	-1.543 6
0.030 5	-0.314 4	0.213 0	-1.575 7
0.043 9	-0.455 6	0.287 0	-1.665 5
0.065 8	-0.688 7	0.322 0	-1.665 0
0.071 7	-0.747 1	0.425 0	-1.636 1
0.077 6	-0.806 1	0.458 4	-1.596 2
0.088 5	-0.905 6	0.462 4	-1.605 3
0.108 2	-1.076 6	0.576 8	-1.415 7
0.116 5	-1.154 8	0.595 6	-1.372 4
0.126 9	-1.215 3	0.617 9	-1.340 8
0.131 4	-1.249 1	0.652 0	-1.247 9
0.137 2	-1.277 8	0.848 0	-0.612 2
0.163 3	-1.409 7	0.925 4	-0.310 3
0.169 6	-1.452 5	1	0
0.179 0	-1.484 4		

The excess molar volumes of [12-crown-4 $\{(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_4\}$ + water] are shown in Fig. 3, together with those for [dimethyl triethylene glycol $\{\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{H}\}$ + water]^{8,10}. The two data sets have remarkably similar profiles. Fig. 4 shows the excess molar volumes for the linear and cyclic diethers. Here, the difference between the two sets of values is far more substantial than is the case for the tetraethers. It is also noteworthy that there is relatively little difference in the extreme values of V^E for the two linear polyethers, while there is a large

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes (V^E) for binary aqueous organic mixtures vs mole fraction (x) at 25° . The markers represent the experimental values: (o) [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work), (●) [MeOEtOMe + water] (Ref. 5), (□) [MeOEtOH + water] (Ref. 1) and (■) [HOEtOH + water] (Ref. 4). The curves have been obtained from four-segment analyses and coefficients from Table 4; full lines: [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work); dotted lines: [MeOEtOH + water] (Ref. 1); dash-dotted lines: [HOEtOH + water] (Ref. 4).

difference between the extreme values of the two cyclic ethers.

Fig. 2. Excess molar volumes (V^E) for binary aqueous organic mixtures vs mole fraction (x) at 25° . The markers represent the experimental values: (o) [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work), (●) [MeO(EtO)₂Me + water] (Ref. 8) and (■) [MeO(EtO)₃Me + water] (Ref. 8). The curves have been obtained from four-segment analyses and coefficients from Table 4; full lines: [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work); dotted lines: [MeO(EtO)₂Me + water] (Ref. 8); dash-dotted lines: [MeO(EtO)₃Me + water] (Ref. 8).

Fig. 3. Excess molar volumes (V^E) for binary aqueous organic mixtures vs mole fraction (x) at 25° . The markers represent the experimental values: (o) [12-crown-4 + water] (this work), (●) [MeO(EtO)₃Me + water] (Ref. 8) and (■) [MeO(EtO)₃Me + water] (Ref. 10). The curves have been obtained from four-segment analyses and coefficients from Table 4; full lines: [12-crown-4 + water] (this work); dotted lines: [MeO(EtO)₃Me + water] (Ref. 8).

It has been suggested that the magnitude of the excess molar volumes (V^E) might be associated with differences in the size and the shape of the molecules, in the intermolecular interaction energy

Fig. 4. Excess molar volumes (V^E) for binary aqueous organic mixtures vs mole fraction (x) at 25° . The markers represent the experimental values: (o) [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work), (●) [MeOEtOMe + water] (Ref. 5), (□) [1,4-dioxane + water] (Ref. 12) and (■) [1,4-dioxane + water] (Ref. 11). The curves have been obtained from four-segment analyses and coefficients from Table 4; full lines: [MeOEtOMe + water] (this work); dotted lines: [1,4-dioxane + water] (Ref. 12).

TABLE 3—EXCESS MOLAR VOLUMES FOR (12-CROWN-4 + WATER) MIXTURES AT 25°

x	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	x	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0	0	0.116 5	-1.050 2
0.004 41	-0.042 3	0.145 9	-1.171 1
0.005 12	-0.049 4	0.181 9	-1.247 3
0.007 59	-0.075 8	0.221 0	-1.299 6
0.009 29	-0.093 4	0.268 4	-1.323 1
0.010 89	-0.106 9	0.282 3	-1.317 1
0.012 27	-0.124 7	0.308 7	-1.311 3
0.016 8	-0.173 2	0.327 4	-1.292 0
0.017 2	-0.178 8	0.336 8	-1.289 1
0.017 7	-0.183 3	0.389 0	-1.224 9
0.019 6	-0.205 3	0.389 9	-1.226 7
0.028 8	-0.297 6	0.409 5	-1.190 8
0.037 2	-0.389 7	0.489 5	-1.056 8
0.040 9	-0.429 4	0.556 2	-0.963 8
0.045 1	-0.481 7	0.568 7	-0.913 3
0.050 5	-0.533 3	0.646 4	-0.753 7
0.057 7	-0.603 4	0.720 0	-0.614 0
0.066 6	-0.687 7	0.845 7	-0.352 5
0.073 0	-0.743 9	0.876 1	-0.275 0
0.087 3	-0.860 3	1	0

between like and unlike molecules, and with structural changes, such as changes in the correlation of molecular orientations¹⁸. It is worth noting that the dependence of V^E upon composition tends to resemble that of the excess molar isentropic compressibilities (K_S^E)¹⁹. Since (K_S^E) measurements tend to have an excellent internal consistency, it would be worthwhile to obtain detailed values for these systems.

Curve-fitting procedures were used to estimate the level of internal consistency of our data sets, and to compare this level with those of the corresponding data sets taken out of the literature. A widely used approach to analysing the excess molar properties of binary liquid mixtures has been proposed by Redlich and Kister²⁰; a simplified form of their equations is

$$V^E = x(1-x) \sum_{i=0}^k A_i (1-2x)^i \quad (1)$$

where x is most frequently the mole fraction, x ,

of one of the components. It should be emphasised that this approach is ill-suited to fitting asymmetric curves; the coefficients, A_i , whose number, $k + 1$, is determined by regression and which are evaluated by least-squares optimisation, have no recognisable physical significance. Much better quality of fit is obtained by other procedures which are designed to accommodate the abrupt variations in the composition dependence of the excess molar properties of (amphiphile + water) systems at low amphiphile concentrations. Among them, the four-segment model represents an attempt to formalise and quantify that approach to data interpretation. It embodies the concept of the segmentation of the total composition range into four distinct regions. The V^E -values for each segment are assigned a distinct simple polynomial function of mole fraction. The ranges, names and polynomial functions for the four segments are : (i) $0 \leq x \leq x_1$, water-rich, cubic, (ii) $x_1 \leq x \leq x_2$, transitional, quartic, (iii) $x_2 \leq x \leq x_3$, central, quadratic, and (iiii) $x_3 \leq x \leq 1$, amphiphile-rich, cubic.

The analysis requires the location of three segment junctions. Optimum values of the three segment junction compositions were determined by means of a 'Simplex' procedure, with appropriate safe-guards against settling for false minima.

The analytical model has undergone several evolutionary stages^{1-4,21,22}. The equations used in this work correspond to its most recent form²³. The set of equations is constrained so that V^E and dV^E/dx are both single valued at each of the three segment junctions. This provides a model with eight independent variables, namely : (i) a_w , the excess apparent (and also partial) molar volume of the amphiphile at infinite aqueous dilutions; it can be converted to the infinite dilution apparent molar volume by the addition of the molar volume of the pure amphiphile, (ii) b_w , which is associated with solute-solute pair interactions, while c_w is thought to be more closely related to cluster formation, (iii) q_w , the excess molar volume of some type of hypothetical standard state of water and, as such, may be regarded as a measure of the effects of the changes in the nature of aqueous self-ag-

gregation²⁴, (iv) q_A , plays a similar role for the amphiphile, (v) b_L , is thought to be associated with the interactions between amphiphile and aqueous microphases, involving only the polar head groups of the amphiphiles which are, of course, the same, (vi) a_A , the excess partial molar volume of water at infinite dilution in the amphiphilic solvent, (vii) it is not obvious how one should interpret the values of the parameter b_T . The values of these parameters are reported in Table 4.

Finally, one of the questions that is frequently posed concerning hydroorganic mixtures is whether or not one can find evidence of clear group additivity schemes among the partial (or apparent) molar volumes of the organic solutes at infinite aqueous dilution. We have assembled values for this quantity for a number of systems. The nine systems are $\text{HOCH}_2(\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2)_n\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ + ($n = 0-3$), $\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2(\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2)_n\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3$ + ($n = 0-3$) and $\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ + water. We note that these organic species can be regarded as being constructed from the three component groups : HOCH_2- , CH_3OCH_2- and $-\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2-$.

Excess partial molar volumes at infinite dilution were evaluated by means of four segment analyses of the various excess molar volume data sets. Addition of the molar volumes of the pure organic species gave the partial molar volumes themselves. The

effectiveness of the group additivity principle is nicely demonstrated by the results shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) OF SOME GLYCOLS AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS AT INFINITE AQUEOUS DILUTION AT 25°

Compound	Exp.	Calc.*
HOEtOH	54.58	54.86
HO(EtO) ₂ OH	92.28	92.01
HO(EtO) ₃ OH	129.04	129.16
HO(EtO) ₄ OH	166.35	166.32
MeOEtOH	75.08	74.90
MeOEtOMe	94.87	94.94
MeO(EtO) ₂ Me	132.41	132.09
MeO(EtO) ₃ Me	169.28	169.24
MeO(EtO) ₄ Me	206.03	206.40

*Group contributions: HOCH_2- : $27.43 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, CH_3OCH_2- : $47.47 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2-$: $37.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

Experimental

The sample of dimethyl ethylene glycol (Aldrich; 99.9%) was tested for peroxides and found to have minimal amounts. The purity of 12-crown-4 sample (Sigma; 98%) was determined by gas chromatography. Both polyethers were used without attempts at further purification. All samples were used directly from the manufacturers' bottles, which were kept tightly sealed to minimise absorption of atmospheric moisture

TABLE 4—OPTIMISED FOUR-SEGMENT MODEL PARAMETERS FOR V^E ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) OF AQUEOUS ORGANIC MIXTURES AT 25°

Parameter	MeOEtOMe ^a	HOEtOMe ^b	HOEtOH ^c	MeO(EtO) ₂ Me ^d	MeO(EtO) ₃ Me ^d	12CR4 ^e	6CR2 ^e
x_1	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.05	0.085	0.07
x_2	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.50
x_3	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.60	0.80
a_w	-9.763 6	-4.263 3	-1.288 4	-10.631	-12.345	-9.996 5	-4.833 3
b_w	-22.578	-19.669	-4.472 9	-57.249	-86.839	-24.539	-1.550 5
c_w	156.38	94.646	18.195	505.35	922.75	257.04	63.287
q_w	-1.218 5	-0.483 0	-0.098 1	-1.375 8	-1.827 1	-1.467 9	-0.884 2
q_A	0.161 8	0.637 7	0.208 1	1.090 2	0.034 6	0.276 2	0.090 8
b_L	-4.097 0	-4.033 2	-1.557 6	-5.528 6	-1.575 8	-1.517 0	-0.824 4
a_A	-4.272 3	-2.283 8	-0.871 6	-3.745 5	-1.577 5	-2.401 9	-0.843 3
b_T	0.106 0	0.296 2	0.131 5	1.031 7	0.784 8	0.916 7	0.173 9
$\sigma(V^E)$	0.005 5	0.000 9	0.000 7	0.003 3	0.002 5	0.005 5	0.000 9

^aThis work. ^bRef. 1. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 8. ^eRef. 12.

and carbon dioxide. There was no evidence of any significant density changes of neat samples over the period required to collect a complete set of aqueous mixtures density. Aqueous mixtures were prepared by mass at room temperature with a precision of 0.1 mg, using double-distilled deionised water, which were stored in tight polyethylene containers. The calculated values of the mole fractions are believed to be reliable to less than 1×10^{-4} . The molar quantities are based on the relative atomic mass table of I.U.P.A.C.²⁵.

Densities (ρ) of the pure components and their aqueous mixtures were measured using a Sodev 03D densimeter, which employed the vibrating-tube principle²⁶. Before each series of measurements, the instrument was calibrated with reagent grade methanol and thoroughly deionised double-distilled water, using density $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(25^\circ) = 997.048 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ as given by Kell¹⁵. The density difference for any liquid relative to pure water is given by

$$\Delta\rho = K (\tau^2 - \tau_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2) \quad (2)$$

where K is the calibration constant, and τ the period of vibration, determined by means of a high-resolution digital frequency meter, an integral part of the densimeter. The temperature of the densimeter was maintained at $25.00 \pm 0.02^\circ$ by means of a Sodev CT-L programmable circulating thermostat. Each density measurement was bracketed by two water measurements in order to avoid any possible detrimental effects arising from instrument drift. The sensitivity of the densimeter corresponded to a precision of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The reproducibility of the density estimated at $25.00 \pm 0.02^\circ$ was found to be of the order of $\pm 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The molar volumes (V) were readily calculated from the measured densities and the molar excess volumes V^E were obtained assuming ideal mole fraction additivity of molar volumes, from the following equation,

$$V^E = \frac{x_A M_A + x_B M_B}{\rho} - \frac{x_A M_A}{\rho_A^*} - \frac{x_B M_B}{\rho_B^*} \quad (3)$$

where ρ , ρ_A^* and ρ_B^* are respectively the density

of the mixtures and of the pure components A and B, whose molar masses are M_A and M_B .

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